

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE BEST EXAMPLES OF THE WORLD LITERATURE FOR THE KAZAKH READERS

Mashakova A.K.

PhD in Philology,

M.O. Auezov Institute of Literature and Art,

Almaty, Kazakhstan

Abstract

For a deep and comprehensive study of the history of literature of the Kazakh people, it is necessary to take into account the achievements of literatures of other peoples. The article discusses the process of translating the works of foreign writers into the Kazakh language. The distinctive features of this process in the Soviet period and in the period of independence of Kazakhstan have been noted. It is shown how specific work on translation of the works of the world literature into the State language is currently being carried out in Kazakhstan.

Keywords: literary translation, the Kazakh language, the world literature

Literary translation is an impetus for the cultural rapprochement of the peoples, the establishment of friendship and mutual understanding between them. Introducing domestic literature to the high achievements of the world cultural tradition, the translation expands its horizons, multiplying its possibilities, while exerting its fruitful influence on its development.

During the Soviet period, the process of translation of the works of foreign literature into Kazakh was quite intensive. The State paid much attention to the literary translation. At that time, foreign literature was subject to a strict selection in accordance with ideological criteria. At the Union of Writers of Kazakhstan, there was a commission for literary translation; the need to conduct serious and diligent work on translation of literary masterpieces from other languages into Kazakh was universally recognized. For several decades, dozens of classical works of the world literature have been translated into the Kazakh language. In those years, the formation of professional literary translation took place in Kazakhstan. It is noteworthy that along with professional translators, the writers-translators and poets-translators appeared. This was especially observed in regard to the translation of poetic works, since in this case it is necessary to have a poetic gift.

The process of translation of the works of foreign oriental authors into Kazakh was quite active. "Only in Soviet times the Kazakh people got the opportunity to read the works of the world's great writers such as Firdaws, Nizami, Navoi, Magtumbuly, Rabindranath Tagore, Persian, Japanese, Chinese, Korean, Vietnamese, Arabic, Indian classics in talented translations into their native language» [1, p. 3].

The direct translation of Goethe's immortal creation "Faust" from German into Kazakh became an exceptional fact, which was done by Medeu Kurmanov and published in 1982. In fact, it was the first direct literary translation from Western European language into Kazakh. Thus, the traditions of the own school of literary translation have developed in Kazakhstan.

In the first years of the period of independence of Kazakhstan, the literary translation of the world literature into the Kazakh language and the works of

modern Kazakh writers and poets into the world languages took place in difficult socio-cultural circumstances. This process was characterized by a certain slowdown in the translation process.

Trying to explain the reasons for the decline in the pace of literary translation in modern Kazakhstan, one should indicate the internal situation in the country, when the entire Kazakh society was facing difficult period of economic and socio-political transformations. The lack of purposeful and systematic work in the field of literary translation, insufficient funding has led to a decrease in the number of professional translators. In this regard, the Kazakh writer Rollan Seisenbayev, editor-in-chief of the magazine of literature of the world peoples "Amanat" said the following: "Now it is incredibly difficult to find a good translator - the old masters have already gone, but there is no worthy replacement for them. The same is true in the West. In Kazakhstan, this situation is even more aggravated. The problem needs to be solved at the State level" [2]. By the way, in 2006, the publishing house "Amanat" under the direction of Rollan Seisenbayev published a collection of poems by the Polish poet Adam Mickiewicz in the Kazakh language.

In recent years, when a period of political and economic stabilization has been established in our country, all the necessary prerequisites have been created for the further development of the spiritual culture of Kazakhstan. So, at the moment, the situation regarding the development of literary translation and popularization of Kazakh literature in the world, as well as the popularization of the achievements of the world literature in Kazakhstan, is gradually improving thanks to the translation into the Kazakh language. The State programs began to pay attention to the issues of literary translation. In particular, one of the directions of the State Program of the Republic of Kazakhstan "Cultural Heritage" for 2004-2011 was the publication of the achievements of the world classics in the State language. The "Library of the World Literature" series includes the most outstanding literary masterpieces of the authors from Europe, America, Africa and Asia. An example is the publication in 2004 of one of the best

works of the classic of French literature Stendhal - the novel "Red and Black" in the Kazakh language. The translation was done by the Doctor of Philology, professor Zhumagali Ismagulov, who has extensive experience in translational work.

During the period of independence of Kazakhstan, the process of translating foreign works into the Kazakh language can be observed through the publications in Kazakh literary magazines. Thus, in the journal "Zhuldyz" ("Star"), which is published in the Kazakh language, the works of the world classics are published. For example, you can read "Aesop" in the translation of the writer Turysbek Sauketayev, the stories of Akutagawa Ryunosuke in the Kazakh language. The translation was done by the writer Tolegen Kazhybayev and others. The existence of a permanent column "Great Personalities" in the journal, in which the biographies of the famous foreign writers and poets began to appear, is a positive aspect.

Among the poetic works, the fact of translation of the poems by the Romanian poet Mikhail Eminescu into Kazakh in 2000 by the poet Shomishbai Sariyev should be noted.

An important positive factor at this stage was the availability of direct translations from foreign languages into the Kazakh language. In 2013 Zhanar Konayeva translated "The Little Prince" by Antoine de Saint-Exupery from French into Kazakh. The book [3] was published in the Kazakh language by the Atamura publishing house, which publishes not only fiction, but also textbooks. When publishing this book, original illustrations by the French writer were used. Direct translations from German into Kazakh are carried out by the translator Almagambet Turekhanov. He translated a number of works by German writers such as Armin Greim and Gerhard Rappus, John Castle, Peter Hartlin, which were published as separate books in Kazakhstani publishing houses. However, in addition to such isolated facts, the main part of translations from foreign languages continues to be carried out through the mediation of the Russian language.

In 2020, thanks to the Kazakh publishing house "Steppe & World Publishing", the book "Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone" by British writer J. K. Rowling became available to the Kazakh readers. Dinara Mazon, Sayat Mukhamediyar and Narkez Berikkyzy worked on the translation [4]. In the same year, in Kazakhstan, on the initiative of the Director of the publishing house "Steppe & World Publishing" R. Sairan-Kader, the book "Tentek balakaydyn kundeligi" [4] was published - this is a translation of one of the books in the series "Diary of a Wimpy Kid" by the American writer Jeff Kinney about the boy Greg Heffley who was keeping a diary. The main feature of the book is that it is published in two languages - English and Kazakh, so it can be considered a manual for learning languages. It should be noted that the publishing house "Steppe & World Publishing" is doing a great job aimed at publishing foreign works for children in the Kazakh language. In addition to the above books, two fairy tales by the English writer Julia Donaldson "The Rhyming

Rabbit" ("Akyn koyan") and "The Gruffalo" ("The Gruffalo") were published. The story of a kind monster named Gruffalo who is living in the forest and a mouse was translated into Kazakh by Galym Bokash [5].

In 2022, the presentation of the books "The Godfather" by Mario Puzo and "Once Upon a Time in America" by Harry Gray in the Kazakh language, translated by Suindik Zhanysbay and Rymbala Smailova, took place. These bestsellers are the most popular in the world, including among the Kazakh readers. It is interesting that these two books were published thanks to the Karaganda Regional Center for Language Learning, whose employees attract sponsors for the publication of the books.

New works on the book market of Kazakhstan are the foreign prose works in the Kazakh language, which were published in 2021-2022 by the «Foliant» publishing house (Nursultan). A review of the bookstores showed that among the authors of the books published in the Kazakh language there are American (Stephen King, Herman Melville, Ken Kesey, Dan Brown, Francis Scott Fitzgerald, Mark Twain, Ray Bradbury), English (Charles Dickens, Herbert Wells, Jane Austen), German (Erich Maria Remarque), Turkish (Orhan Pamuk, Reshat Nuri Guntekin), Japanese (Kazuo Ishiguro) writers. Attention should be paid to the translators of these books, many of them are engaged in direct translations from foreign languages. For example, Mira Sembaykyzy, Duysenali Alimakyn, Lira Konys translate from English, Gulnaz Fayzulla translates from Turkish.

So, for a deep and comprehensive study of the history of literature of the Kazakh people, it is necessary to take into account the achievements of the literatures of other peoples. Currently, certain work on translating the works of the world literature into the State language is being carried out in Kazakhstan.

References

1. Lizunova E.V. From the depths of centuries to the present day // Kazakh literature and its connections with the literatures of the peoples of Asia and Africa. – Alma-Ata: M.O. Auezov ILA, 1973. – P. 1-15 [in Rus.].
2. Words for export // Liter. – 2006. URL: <http://www.liter.kz> [in Rus.].
3. Bakytova A. New friends of the little prince // Kazakhstanskaya Pravda. – 2013. – October 8. – P. 14 [in Rus.].
4. Begaliyeva R. What to read to a child and a teenager in the Kazakh language // Caravan. – 22.10.2020. URL: <https://www.caravan.kz/news/chtopochitat-rebenku-i-podrostku-na-kazahskom-yazyke-683732/> [in Rus.].
5. Aisarov D. The famous English fairy tale "The Gruffalo" was translated into the Kazakh language // Information Bureau. – 2019. – November 26. URL: <https://informburo.kz/novosti/izvestnuyu-angliyskiyuskazku-gruffalo-pereveli-na-kazahskiy-yazyk.html> [in Rus.].